

The Use of Social Network Tools in Iran and the Impacts of Improper Communication and Transparency on Information Security and Privacy

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Abstract: Although popular social networking tools such as Facebook and Twitter are blocked in Iran, the number of Iranian users using such services is increasing day by day. This means that an increasing number of Iranian users have taken the habit of using commercial anti-censorship tools to access blocked content - which is against the Iranian ICT laws. Studies show that the enormous amount of information leakage on social networks has resulted in numerous incidents of robberies, harassment and identity theft. While countries such as UK and US are making efforts to increase peoples' awareness about required security and privacy precautions, the Iranian authorities are mainly focusing on preventing and discouraging the use of social network tools and are unwilling to accept the increasing usage. Our survey results, from 511 Facebook users residing in Iran, indicate that Iranian users have a very limited knowledge about potential privacy and security risks of using anti-censorship tools and online social networks such as Facebook. We evaluate the potential security and privacy threats for the people and national security and suggest recommendations on how to improve this condition.

Keywords: Social Network, Internet Filtering, Anti-censorship tool, Privacy, ICT in Iran.